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<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/>

Nextfood - Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Practice Abstract #2: Action research protocol

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Action research is essentially learning by doing, and reflecting upon the experiences. An intuitive approach recommended for anyone who is trying to improve a situation they are in. A central part of the Nextfood project is the 12 case studies conducted in 10 countries on 3 continents. All these cases are attempting to transform their education models to align with the Nextfood approach. Not only are we trying to make the change, but we are also researching the process and the outcomes. In order to ensure a synchronised data collection, this research protocol provides instructions on how to gather and analyse data from the activities performed during the case work. This involves recording workshops, gathering the responses from students and teachers and synthesising these in a streamlined fashion. The protocol ensures that all cases have a shared research strategy, but also allows each case to fit the data collection to their specific context.

By doing research this way we will get an improved understanding of what it takes to implement alternative education models that are better fit to deal with present and future challenges. Simultaneously we will improve the education for the learners who are involved in the cases so that they are already better equipped to deal with the complex challenges.